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A facile approach to epoxy/graphene platelets nanocomposites

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Keywords: *Epoxy, fracture, graphene, electrical conductivity, nanocomposites*

1 General Introduction

Since 1859, extensive research has been conducted concerning graphite and graphite modification [1-4]. Graphite comprises layers of interconnected hexagonal carbon rings arranged in parallel, where each sheet of carbon atoms is offset by one-half of a unit such that alternate sheets are in the same position [5]. In the basal plane, each sp³ carbon atom forms covalent bonds along internuclear axis with one distributed bonding that resides above and below the graphite atoms. This distributed bonding gives rise to delocalized electrons that make graphite electrically conducting. Along the basal plane, graphite possesses an exceptionally high modulus (~1TPa), excellent electrical and thermal conductivities, and a low coefficient of thermal expansion. Graphene is just a single layer of graphite. When graphite is modified and mixed with polymers by appropriate routes, it is able to disperse as graphene platelets (GP). These characteristics of graphite drive new approaches to fabricating high-performance, functional polymer nanocomposites.

Epoxy is widely used in various engineering fields from structural composites to microelectronic, due to their excellent bonding strength, chemical resistance, and electrical, mechanical and thermal properties. However, the high crosslink density makes these materials inherently brittle, leading to poor resistance to crack propagation [6-9]. Nowadays, toughening epoxy by graphene has become an interesting method due to the amazing properties of graphene. Potential applications for this type of material include electromagnetic shielding, electrochemical capacitors, light emitting devices, antistatic, corrosion resistance, etc [10,11]. Epoxy/graphene composites have already showed potential in application in thermoelectric power generation [12]. However, composites associated

with good electrical conductivity still remains a challenge.

Therefore, this study will develop a facile method to synthesizing epoxy/GP nanocomposites, and investigate their mechanical and electrical properties. The method mainly comprises expanding graphite by thermal shock and dispersing graphene in epoxy by sonication. The investigation is carried out using tensile test, fracture toughness and electrical conductivity test.

2 Preparation and Submission

2.1 Materials

Acid-treated Graphite, Asbury 3494, was provided by Asbury Carbons, Asbury, NJ. Epoxy resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, Araldite-F) with epoxide equivalent weight 182-196 g/equiv, was purchased from Ciba-Geigy, Australia. Two types of hardeners, namely polyoxypropylene (J230) and 4,4-diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS), were used to mix with epoxy at 100:33 and 100:30, respectively.

2.2 Synthesis of epoxy/graphene nanocomposites

1 g of acid-treated graphite was first expanded in a furnace at 700°C for 1 minute to produce expanded graphite (GP) which was then suspended at 1 wt% in 100 g tetrahydrofuran (THF) using a metal container. The container was covered and treated in an ultrasonic bath (200 watts and 42 kHz) below 30°C for 2 hours to obtain a uniform suspension of GP. DGEBA dissolved in acetone was added to the mixture and mixed by a mechanical stirrer for 30 minutes, followed by sonication under 30°C for 1 hour. The solvent was evaporated through mechanically mixing at 110°C for 1 hour. Then the mixture was highly degassed in a vacuum oven at 120°C to remove trace of solvent and air bubbles. Stoichiometric amount of hardener D230 or DDS

was added and mixed using the mechanical stirrer at 50°C for 2 min or at 130°C for 20 min, respectively. The resultant mixture was then highly degassed in the oven for 5 min. The mixture was poured into a rubber mould, followed by curing (i) at 80°C for 3 hrs and at 120°C for 12 hrs for D230-cured system and (ii) at 140°C for 14 hrs for DDS-cured system.

2.3 Characterization techniques

Tensile testing was performed at 0.5 mm/min at room temperature using an Instron 5567. An Instron extensometer 2630-100 was used to collect accurate displacement data for modulus which were calculated using 0.005–0.2 % strain.

Fracture toughness testing was carried out using an instantly propagated crack, which was introduced to each sample by a razor blade tapping method [13, 14]. Six specimens were tested for each set of data at 0.5 mm/min. The Plane-strain fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and Critical strain energy release rate (G_{Ic}) of CT specimens were calculated and verified according to ISO13586.

Electrical conductivity measurement was obtained at room temperature through a conventional two-point-probe conductivity measurement device (Agilent). The test was conducted according to ASTM D257-99 and five average values were taken to measure volume resistivity at 5 V.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile properties

Figure 1 shows the Young's moduli and tensile strength of neat epoxy and its nanocomposites. In Figure 1(a), Young's modulus increases obviously with the fraction of graphene platelets (GP). At 4 wt%, the modulus increases 17% for DDS-cured system and 13% for J230-cured system. The modulus improvement is attributed to (i) the exceptionally high modulus 1TPa of GP compared to epoxy matrix, and (ii) the possibly good dispersion of graphene platelets in matrix, which imposes restriction on the molecular motion of epoxy upon tensile loading. DDS cured-system shows the higher modulus improvement compared to J230 cured-system, because the DDS backbone contains benzene and sulfone groups which provide the network with rigidity [15, 16].

In contrast to Young's modulus, tensile strength decreases with filler content as shown in Figure 1(b).

A similar behavior has also been observed for nanoclay-toughened epoxy [14]. The reduction of tensile strength was caused by the incorporation of graphene platelets which actually work as defects under tensile loading.

Figure 1 Variation of (a) Young's modulus and (b) tensile strength for epoxy/graphene nanocomposites

3.3 Fracture toughness

Figure 2 illustrates the fracture toughness and fracture energy release rate of the two systems. In Figure 2(a), fracture toughness increases steadily with graphene fractions until 2 wt%, and then decreases slightly. The fracture toughness of DDS-cured system increases from 0.46 to 1.13 MPa·m^{1/2} at 4 wt%, while for J230-cured system, it increases from 0.66 to 1.09 MPa·m^{1/2}. The maximum fracture toughness values, 1.23 MPa·m^{1/2} for DDS-cured system and 1.17 MPa·m^{1/2} for the other system, were observed at 2.0 wt% for both systems.

The fracture energy release rates for both systems show a similar trend in Figure 2(b): increasing steadily from 0–2 wt%, followed by a slight reduction. The energy release rate increases from

229.5 to 552.4 J·m⁻² for DDS-cured system and from 86.9 to 461.2 J·m⁻² for J230-cured system. This increase could be explained by: (1) GP work as stress concentrators, which are able to absorb large fracture energy when local stress exceeds the strength of particle/matrix interface, (2) graphene platelets act as obstacles as soon as crack propagates. When a propagated crack encounters obstacles, it may temporarily pin and form a new fracture crack, and (3) crack tip blunts due to the debonding of particle/matrix interface [17, 18].

Figure 2 Variation of (a) fracture toughness and (b) fracture energy for epoxy/graphene nanocomposites

3.3 Electrical conductivity study

Figure 3 presents the electrical resistivity of neat epoxy and its nanocomposites. Both neat epoxy resins are essentially insulative, showing electrical resistivity at $1.1\text{--}1.2 \times 10^{15} \Omega\cdot\text{m}$. Upon compounding with electrically conductive GP, the electrical resistivity decreases significantly; there is no obvious percolation threshold; both systems show a similar trend. The increase in conductivity is attributed to the formation of an electrically conductive network produced by GP, providing an

electron path for transmittance [19, 20].

Figure 3 Variation of electrical conductivity for epoxy/graphene nanocomposites

4 Conclusion

Epoxy/graphene nanocomposites were prepared by a facile approach using a common furnace, a sonication bath and a mechanical stirrer. Two systems were fabricated using Jeffamine D230 (J230) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenyle sulfone (DDS). Although DDS-cured epoxy showed a higher stiffness, graphene platelets toughened it better than J230-cured epoxy. Both systems showed similar improvement of electrical conductivity.

Acknowledgements: JM thanks Asbury Carbons for the provision of acidified graphite.

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